

**THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FINTECH AND CO₂
EMISSIONS IN ASIA:
THE MODERATING ROLE OF INCOME INEQUALITY**

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of financial technology (Fintech) on CO₂ emissions in nine major Asian economies from 2012 to 2021, with a focus on the moderating role of income inequality. Using a mixed-method approach that combines Generalized Least Squares (GLS), Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and expert interviews, the findings show that Fintech significantly reduces CO₂ emissions. Specifically, a one-unit increase in the Fintech Index corresponds to an 18.2-unit reduction in per capita emissions. However, this effect weakens in countries with high income inequality due to limited digital access among low-income populations. The interaction between Fintech and the Gini coefficient has a positive and significant effect on emissions, indicating that income inequality diminishes the environmental benefits of Fintech. Additionally, GDP and foreign direct investment (FDI) are positively associated with emissions, while renewable energy consumption significantly reduces CO₂ emissions. Expert insights from Vietnam highlight barriers to inclusive green finance, including digital illiteracy and infrastructure gaps. The study contributes empirical evidence on the Fintech-environment nexus and emphasizes that Fintech may be insufficient in reducing CO₂ emissions in Asian countries unless equality, financial inclusion, and supportive green policy frameworks are in place.

Keywords: Asia, CO₂ emissions, digital finance, Fintech, income inequality

1. Introduction

CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion are widely recognized as the leading cause of climate change. The Asia-Pacific region, which accounts for nearly 50% of global CO₂ emissions, continues to experience rapid industrial expansion driven by carbon-intensive energy systems. This raises urgent concerns about how fast-growing economies in the region can transition toward more sustainable models.

In this context, financial technology (Fintech) has emerged as a potential catalyst for green transformation by promoting sustainable consumption, improving financial inclusion, and enabling efficient allocation of green capital. However, the effectiveness of Fintech in reducing greenhouse gas emissions may be significantly constrained by income inequality. These disparities limit the ability of low-income groups to access digital infrastructure and financial services, thereby weakening the positive environmental impact Fintech could deliver. This study addresses this gap by examining how income inequality influences the relationship between Fintech development and CO₂ emissions. The analysis uses a panel dataset including nine Asian economies - including China, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, the Philippines, South Korea, Thailand, and Vietnam - from 2012 to 2021. These countries were chosen due to their strategic roles in regional carbon emissions and varying stages of Fintech adoption. The study

applies Generalized Least Squares (GLS) regression to address heteroskedasticity commonly observed in macro-panel data. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is used to construct composite indices for Fintech and economic development, while expert interviews in Vietnam provide practical validation. This research makes three main contributions. First, it strengthens empirical studies evaluating the moderating effect of income inequality on the Fintech - environment nexus in Asian economies. Second, it employs a multi-method approach, combining quantitative modeling with qualitative validation. Third, it offers implications to guide Fintech strategies and green development transitions in Asian economies. This paper is structured as follows: Section 1 introduces the study, Section 2 reviews related literature, Section 3 describes the methodology, Section 4 presents the results, Section 5 validates the model, Section 6 offers policy recommendations, and Section 7 concludes the paper.

2. Literature Review

This section reviews the theoretical foundations and empirical evidence on the interrelationships among FinTech development, income inequality, and CO₂ emissions in Asian economies, identifying key mechanisms and gaps.

FinTech's potential environmental impacts are framed by four established theories. The Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) and Green Finance Theory together suggest that early economic growth raises emissions and inequality, but as digital-finance tools such as green bonds, concessional credit, and climate funds become available, they can mobilize capital for renewable-energy projects and begin to bend the EKC downward by reducing CO₂ emissions. The Technology–Environmental–Economic–Social Sustainability Theory (T-EESST) further argues that innovations like FinTech only generate meaningful sustainability gains when integrated into inclusive policy frameworks and supportive infrastructure, ensuring green finance truly reaches underserved communities. Additionally, The Digital Financial Inclusion Theory underscores that broadening digital access to financial services reflected in PCA-based FinTech indices enables low-income populations to engage in renewable-energy financing, although this empowerment diminishes as income inequality rises.

Empirical evidence from China shows that FinTech development can significantly reduce pollutant emissions. Ma et al. (2023) apply a city-level fixed-effects model to 2011–2017 data and find that a 1 % increase in FinTech lowers SO₂ emissions by 0.07 % via digital-finance and green-innovation channels. Wen & Liu (2023) report that FinTech adoption reduces SO₂, solid waste, and CO₂ while improving coordination between pollution control and carbon reduction. At the firm level, Wang et al. (2024) show that a 1 % rise in FinTech growth cuts corporate carbon emissions by 2.07 %, driven by easier access to green finance and sustainable-technology patents.

Income inequality shapes renewable-energy consumption through two channels. Through the economic channel, high inequality fosters individualism, consumerism, and short-termism, leading to rent-seeking behavior and intensive use of non-renewable energy, as societies with high Gini lack collective action and environmental sensitivity. Through the political channel, inequality may reflect weak institutions that fail to incentivize efficient environmental investments—thus inhibiting renewable uptake but in some contexts elites leverage their influence to demand stricter green policies, promoting renewables. Khan et al. (2023) further demonstrate that higher inequality raises CO₂ emissions as affluent groups consume energy less efficiently.

Vo et al. (2023) examine 65 countries and find that while FinTech development generally boosts renewable-energy consumption, this positive effect is significantly weakened under high income inequality.

Finally, macro-drivers such as GDP per capita, FDI, population density, and renewable-energy share also influence CO₂ outcomes. In Indonesia, Aripin et al. (2024) show GDP growth and population exert both short- and long-run effects on CO₂, whereas renewable-energy adoption mitigates emissions.

3. Methodology

3.1. Model

This study investigates the individual effects of Fintech development and income inequality, as well as their interaction effect, on carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions across nine Asian countries over the period 2012 - 2021. The empirical model is developed following recent literature and is specified as follows:

$$CE_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 FIN_{it} + \beta_2 FIN_GINI_{it} + \beta_3 FDI_{it} + \beta_4 REC_{it} + \beta_5 GDP_PD_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ denotes the country and $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ the year. $CO2_{i,t}$ is the dependent variable, representing per capita CO₂ emissions in country i at time t . The main explanatory variables are the Fintech development index $FIN_{i,t}$ constructed using principal component analysis (PCA), and income inequality $GINI_{i,t}$, measured by the Gini coefficient. The interaction term $FIN \times GINI_{i,t}$ is included to examine whether the impact of Fintech on CO₂ emissions is conditional upon the level of income inequality.

In addition, the model controls for relevant macroeconomic and environmental factors. GDP per capita $GDP_{pc\ i,t}$ reflects the level of economic development; foreign direct investment $FDI_{i,t}$ accounts for international capital flows; and renewable energy consumption $REC_{i,t}$ captures a country's transition toward cleaner energy sources. Country fixed effects α_i are incorporated to control for unobserved time-invariant characteristics, while ε_i is the idiosyncratic error term.

3.2. Data

We collect data from several authoritative sources, including the World Development Indicators (WDI) of the World Bank, the Standardized World Income Inequality Database (SWIID) from Harvard University for income inequality, and regional Fintech statistical reports for constructing the Fintech index. The final sample includes nine Asian countries-China, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, the Philippines, South Korea, Thailand, and Vietnam - spanning the period from 2012 to 2021. Table 1 presents the list of countries, while Table 2 provides definitions and sources of all variables used in the analysis.

Our dataset is structured as an unbalanced panel due to data unavailability, particularly on Fintech indicators and the Gini coefficient. This is a common feature in cross-country studies, and we address it using listwise deletion to ensure consistency across observations. All empirical analyses are conducted using Python3, which provides robust techniques for unbalanced panel estimation. The dependent variable is carbon dioxide emissions per capita (metric tons), obtained from WDI. The key independent variable, Fintech development, is proxied by a composite index constructed using principal component analysis (PCA) based on ATM density, internet penetration, and mobile subscriptions. While ATM density may traditionally be associated with conventional banking infrastructure, in emerging Asian economies it still serves as a critical access point to digital financial services. Studies such as Wang et al. (2024) and Ma et al. (2023) have included ATM penetration as a proxy for FinTech access in contexts where mobile banking is not yet fully inclusive. In this study, ATM density complements internet and mobile usage to reflect early-stage digital financial infrastructure, especially in rural or low-income areas, thus capturing the broader scope of financial digitization.

Income inequality is captured by the Gini coefficient, and we include an interaction term ($FIN \times GINI$) to test moderating effects. Control variables include a PCA-based development index (GDP_PD) from GDP per capita and population growth, FDI (% of GDP), and renewable energy consumption (REC). All estimations are conducted in Python 3, using listwise deletion to handle missing values.

Table 2. The descriptions of variables

Variable		Description	Source
Dependent variable			
CO ₂ emissions	CO ₂	CO ₂ emissions per capita (metric tons)	WDI
Independent variables			
Fintech development	FIN	PCA-based composite index of Fintech	
Income inequality	GINI	Gini coefficient of disposable income	SWIID
Interaction term	FIN × GINI	Interaction between Fintech development and income inequality	
Control variables			
Economic development	GDP_PD	PCA-based index combining GDP per capita and population growth rate to proxy for economic development	WDI
Foreign direct investment	FDI	Foreign direct investment inflows (% of GDP)	WDI
Renewable energy consumption	REC	Renewable energy consumption as a percentage of total final energy consumption	WDI

Source: Author's compilation from WDI, SWIID, and Fintech data.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Mean	Median	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
CO ₂	5.3	3.9	3.0	0.9	13.0	5.48	-1.02
FIN	35.3	33.0	8.0	0.9	46.5	-2.12	-3.31
GINI	12	12	13,131	1,429	49,145	1.35	3.57
GDP_PD	42.1	10.9	18.8	-3.48	344.1	2.64	5.99
FDI	16.5	15.6	11.6	1.6	37.9	-2.9	-1.46
REC	279	307	136	90	531	-1.24	-0.93

Source: Author's calculation (Python3) using WDI, SWIID, and Fintech data.

3.3. Our empirical estimations

Our empirical approach examines the effect of FinTech development on CO₂ emissions and whether this relationship is moderated by income inequality. We employ the generalized least squares (GLS) method, appropriate for our panel data given the presence of heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation, as confirmed by Breusch-Pagan and Durbin-Watson tests. GLS provides efficient and consistent estimates under these conditions.

To handle multicollinearity and construct composite indices, we use principal component analysis (PCA). The FinTech index is derived from ATM density, internet usage, and mobile subscriptions, while the economic development index (GDP_PD) combines GDP per capita and population growth. A **Hausman test** ($p = 1.0$) confirms no endogeneity bias, supporting the use of GLS without instrumental variables.

In addition, we conduct **structured interviews** with experts from the banking, FinTech, and ESG sectors. These qualitative insights help contextualize the results, especially for the Vietnamese case.

4. Results

4.1. Main regression results

Table 4 presents the results from the GLS regression examining the effects of FinTech development and income inequality on CO₂ emissions across nine Asian countries during 2012–2021. The model demonstrates strong explanatory power, with an R-squared of 0.957, indicating that 95.7% of the variation in CO₂ emissions is captured by the included variables.

Key findings are summarized as follows:

- FinTech development (FIN) is negatively associated with CO₂ emissions and statistically significant at the 1% level ($\beta = -18.222$), supporting Hypothesis 1. This suggests that FinTech may contribute to emissions reduction by enhancing digital access to finance, promoting green financial products, and improving capital allocation efficiency.
- The interaction term (FIN×GINI) is positive and also significant at the 1% level ($\beta = +0.0525$), confirming Hypothesis 2. This implies that income inequality weakens the environmental benefits of FinTech, likely due to limited digital access among disadvantaged populations.
- GDP_PD, a proxy for economic development, exerts a positive and significant effect on emissions, consistent with the Environmental Kuznets Curve framework in early stages of growth.
- Foreign direct investment (FDI) is positively related to CO₂ emissions, providing evidence in support of the Pollution Haven Hypothesis.
- Renewable energy consumption (REC) has a significant negative effect on emissions, highlighting the role of clean energy in environmental mitigation strategies.

Table 4. GLS Regression Results: CO₂ Emissions, FinTech, and Income Inequality

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-value	95% CI
Constant	10.1235	0.201	50.272	***	[9.723, 10.524]
FIN	-18.2220	4.982	-3.658	***	[-27.183, -9.261]
FIN × GINI	0.0525	0.013	4.026	***	[0.027, 0.078]
FDI	6.13×10^{-12}	1.24×10^{-12}	4.952	***	[3.67e-12, 8.59e-12]
REC	-0.2612	0.008	-30.876	***	[-0.278, -0.244]
GDP_PD	1.0684	0.088	12.176	***	[0.894, 1.242]
Model Fit					
R-squared	0.957				
Adj. R-squared	0.954				
F-statistic	369.6				
AIC	224.5				
BIC	239.5				

Significance levels: *** $p < 0.01$

Source: Author's estimation using GLS on panel data (Python3, 2012–2021)

4.2. Qualitative insights

To complement the empirical results and better understand the mechanisms behind the relationship between Fintech, income inequality, and CO₂ emissions, we conducted expert interviews with professionals in the banking, Fintech, and ESG sectors in Vietnam. The interviews offer valuable insights into the practical implementation and social reception of digital financial tools and green finance initiatives.

Experts agreed that Fintech plays an increasingly important role in reducing CO₂ emissions by digitizing financial services, thereby lowering the use of paper and streamlining loan processes. For instance, the transition from traditional paperwork-intensive loan applications to digital platforms such as Smartbanking or VCB Digibank has led to reduced demand for physical documentation and associated environmental costs. As noted by Tran Cong Danh, an expert from BIDV, Fintech applications such as BIDV’s SmartBanking have transformed traditional banking processes by enabling unsecured loans to be processed online, with funds disbursed within minutes. He emphasized that *“The shift toward minimizing paperwork and intermediaries in loan procedures helps reduce paper consumption, preserve green spaces, and ultimately lower carbon emissions”*. However, concerns were raised about the potential indirect emissions linked to the production of electronic devices and infrastructure needed for Fintech operations. Regarding income inequality, interviewees noted that while Fintech platforms offer broader access to financial services, such benefits are not equally distributed. Low-income populations still face barriers such as digital illiteracy, lack of access to smart devices, and limited financial education. Tran Cong Danh further noted that while Fintech holds promise for narrowing wealth gaps by bringing investment opportunities closer to individuals, structural barriers remain in Vietnam. He explained that *“Although the conditions for economic advancement are becoming more accessible, many people are still unable to fully utilize them due to limitations in mindset, investment knowledge, and financial literacy. As a result, the gap between the rich and the poor remains significant”*. As a result, the positive environmental effects of Fintech can be diminished in contexts with high income inequality.

Importantly, experts emphasized the role of financial education and environmental awareness. They argued that Fintech can only achieve its full environmental potential if accompanied by widespread digital inclusion, sustainability-focused communication, and inclusive financial policies. In addition, he highlighted BIDV’s strategic commitment to sustainability, stating that *“Our initiatives include green credit packages, alignment with ESG trends, and a clear roadmap toward Net Zero.”* These developments reflect the growing role of Fintech in supporting environmental and social governance objectives in the Vietnamese banking sector.

4.3. Country-Level Comparison: Indonesia vs. Japan

To explore how income inequality shapes the FinTech-environment relationship, we compare two contrasting cases: Indonesia (Gini = 46.23) and Japan (Gini = 1.03). These countries differ in both inequality levels and digital infrastructure, offering a useful basis for comparison. Using the same GLS specification, we re-estimate the model separately for each country over 2012-2021. Results are reported in Table 5.

Table 5. Summarizes GLS on split samples

Variable	Indonesia (Highest GINI)	Japan (Lowest GINI)
FinTech (FIN)	- 8.471	- 1.229
FIN × GINI	0.181	1.087
FDI	- 3.07×10 ⁻¹²	- 3.41×10 ⁻¹²
REC	- 0.061**	- 0.498***
GDP_PD	- 1.175	- 0.296

R-squared	0.948	0.992
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Significance levels: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: Author's calculation using GLS on split samples ((Python3))

The coefficient of FinTech (FIN) is negative in both Indonesia and Japan, suggesting its potential role in reducing CO₂ emissions, though the effects are not statistically significant-likely due to limited sample size or structural differences. The interaction term (FIN × GINI) is positive in both cases, supporting the hypothesis that income inequality weakens the environmental benefits of FinTech, yet again without statistical significance.

In contrast, renewable energy consumption (REC) significantly reduces emissions in both countries, with a much stronger effect in Japan (-0.498 vs. -0.061), indicating that clean energy policies may be more effective than FinTech in isolation - especially in digitally fragmented economies.

Although FinTech-related coefficients are insignificant, the gap in model fit ($R^2 = 0.948$ vs. 0.992) suggests that FinTech may be more impactful in countries with greater digital equity. These findings reinforce the conclusion that income inequality poses a key barrier to FinTech's environmental potential and underline the need for context-specific digital policy design.

4.4. Robustness Check: Alternative Proxy for FinTech

To validate the robustness of our findings, we construct an alternative FinTech index using principal component analysis (PCA), following the approach of Andriana et al. (2024). The index is based on three standardized indicators: Account ownership at a financial institution or with a mobile money service provider (% of population ages 15+), Individuals using the Internet, and Mobile cellular subscription per 100 people, drawn from World Bank sources for 2011-2021.

The first principal component (PC1), denoted as FIN, captures the shared variance across these variables and serves as a comprehensive proxy for FinTech development. This approach reflects both access to and usage of digital financial services, addressing limitations of infrastructure-based measures.

We re-estimate the baseline GLS model using this FIN index. As shown in Table 6, FinTech remains negatively associated with CO₂ emissions ($\beta = -1.091$, ***), while the interaction with income inequality is positive and significant ($\beta = 0.032$, ***). The model fit is strong ($R^2 = 0.956$), supporting the robustness of our main conclusion.

Table 6. Robustness Check Using PCA-Based FinTech Index

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Significance
Constant	10.1898	0.205	49.776	***
FIN	- 1.0911	0.257	- 4.244	***
FIN × GINI	0.0321	0.007	4.625	***
FDI	6.45×10^{-12}	1.26×10^{-12}	5.125	***
REC	- 0.2670	0.009	- 30.452	***
GDP_PD	1.1189	0.090	12.431	***
R-squared	0.956	-	-	-

Significance levels: *** $p < 0.01$

Source: Author's estimation using GLS and PCA-based FinTech index (Python3).

These findings validate the stability of our results across alternative FinTech constructions. The use of a PCA-based index-rooted in multidimensional digital inclusion-strengthens the empirical credibility of the study and mitigates concerns about potential bias from infrastructure - only proxies. In doing so, we provide further evidence that digital financial development, when inclusively adopted, can play a meaningful role in promoting environmental sustainability.

5. Model validation

To ensure the reliability of our estimation approach, we conduct a series of diagnostic tests to validate model assumptions and justify the use of generalized least squares (GLS) instead of ordinary least squares (OLS).

First, we test for heteroskedasticity using the Breusch-Pagan test. The result yields a p-value of 0.0179, indicating rejection of the null hypothesis of homoskedastic errors. This suggests that the error variance is not constant across observations, violating a core OLS assumption. Second, the Durbin-Watson test statistic is 0.6609, far below the threshold of 1.5. This indicates severe positive autocorrelation in the residuals, further violating classical OLS assumptions. These two findings imply that OLS estimators, while unbiased, are inefficient, and that the standard errors are unreliable, leading to potential bias in hypothesis testing. To address these issues, we adopt the GLS estimation method, which adjusts for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation by reweighting observations based on their estimated error variance structure. This method is particularly appropriate for macro panel data with structural heterogeneity and temporal dependence.

Additionally, we perform the Hausman specification test to assess the potential endogeneity of independent variables. The test returns a p-value of 1.0, suggesting no significant difference between the fixed-effects and random-effects estimators. Thus, we find no evidence of endogeneity, and the GLS estimator remains consistent and efficient without the need for instrumental variables.

6. Policy Recommendations

To fully leverage the environmental benefits of FinTech, policymakers should adopt a dual-focus approach: promoting technological innovation while ensuring inclusive access. Firstly, investing in digital infrastructure - particularly in rural and low-income areas - is essential to bridge the access gap and enable widespread adoption of FinTech services. Secondly, financial and digital literacy programs should target underserved populations to empower them with the skills needed to engage in sustainable financial behaviors and benefit from digital financial tools. Thirdly, governments should integrate FinTech into national climate finance strategies through mechanisms like green credit programs, low-interest digital loans for clean energy, or mobile-based savings platforms for climate adaptation. Public-private partnerships and incentive structures (e.g., tax incentives, innovation grants) can further stimulate the development of environmentally focused FinTech solutions.

Lastly, regulatory frameworks must evolve to ensure sustainability, transparency, and consumer protection. This includes mandatory ESG disclosures for FinTech firms, clear standards for green digital products, and protections for vulnerable users. Cross - ministerial coordination - linking finance, environment, and digital governance - is critical to building an ecosystem where FinTech contributes meaningfully to climate goals while reducing socio-economic disparities.

7. Conclusions

This study provides strong empirical evidence that FinTech development is associated with lower CO₂ emissions in Asian economies. However, this positive impact is significantly weakened in contexts of high income inequality, where digital exclusion limits access to green financial innovations. Through GLS estimation, PCA-based indices, and expert interviews, we demonstrate that the relationship between

FinTech and environmental outcomes is conditional - FinTech alone is not a silver bullet but requires enabling conditions.

Robustness checks, including an alternative FinTech index and a country-level comparison between Japan and Indonesia, support this conclusion: FinTech is more effective in promoting environmental sustainability when digital access is equitable and institutions are supportive. While the study contributes to extending the Environmental Kuznets Curve framework by adding a digital dimension, it also acknowledges key limitations - such as reliance on national-level data and a single environmental indicator. Future research should consider more granular data, additional sustainability metrics, and non-linear modeling techniques.

In summary, FinTech holds considerable promise for enabling a low-carbon transition in Asia. Yet, its success hinges on equitable access, inclusive policy design, and strong institutional support to ensure that its environmental benefits are both scalable and sustainable.

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